

A SURVEY ON THE EFFICACY OF THE ONLINE TEACHING-LEARNING PROCESS DURING COVID 19 PANDEMIC.

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Abstract

The outbreak of Pandemic COVID 19 forcefully closed all the educational institutions all over the world. As a consequence, the Educational scenario has changed overnight with the unprecedented rise of distance learning. With this dramatic shift from the actual classroom to the virtual one, the teachers are undertaking different digital platforms to facilitate e-learning. Initially, the teachers are not well versed with the online digital platforms to impart knowledge to the students. Therefore, the researcher wants to recognize the power elements for the Efficacy of Online Teaching-Learning in the course of COVID-19 Pandemic in B.Ed. institutions in Mumbai as maintained by the Students' Perspective. The Researcher wants to study the merits, difficulties, motivation, and interest level of the students during this online teaching-learning process. This paper wants to place focus on the different aspects of students' views on an online teaching-learning scenario and different modes of online teaching-learning.

Keywords : COVID-19, Online teaching-learning modes, Interest and Motivation level of the students, Technical and Environmental Constraints, B.Ed. Institution.

Introduction

“The world has survived different kinds of crises. People have seen world wars and the economic depression, but the human spirit has endured and survived.” - Swati Rustagi, ¹

COVID-19 pandemic- “Humanity needs leadership and solidarity to defeat the coronavirus.” UNDP. (United Nation Development Programme)

The pandemic of the COVID19 coronavirus is the defining global health crisis of our time and the largest danger we have faced since the Second World War. The virus has spread to every continent except Antarctica since its appearance in Asia late last year. The horrific figure of one million deaths has now been exceeded and the human family is coping under an almost unimaginable burden of loss. But even more than a health crisis, the pandemic is an ongoing socioeconomic crisis, too. It can produce catastrophic social, economic and

¹Swati Rustagi
Director Human Resources at Amazon
Bangalore Urban, Karnataka, India.

political consequences that will leave deep and long-standing scars, stressing every one of the countries it affects.

To plan, react, and recover, every country needs to act immediately. COVID19 symptoms are complex, ranging from mild symptoms to serious illness. Common symptoms include fever, cough, exhaustion, trouble breathing, and loss of taste and smell. People with the same infection could have various symptoms and, over a period, their conditions may change. One person may have a slight fever, coughing, and exhaustion, for example, and another person might

have had a low fever at the onset of the illness and a week later have breathing issues. However, loss of taste combined with a loss of smell is consistent with COVID19 with a specificity of 95 percent in people without the previous ear, nose, and throat (ENT) disorders.

Online teaching-learning modes: With this dramatic change away from the school in many places around the world, some are wondering if post-pandemic acceptance of online learning would continue to exist, and how such a shift will disrupt the education sector worldwide. During this COVID 19 Time, online teaching-learning modes have resulted in schools getting shut down, Online learning for Covid-19 is encouraged for the reasons listed mostly during the lockdown phase. Worldwide. About 1.2 billion kids are out of the classroom worldwide. Online learning for Covid-19 is encouraged for the reasons listed below mostly during the lockdown phase. Emergent methodologies of Govt. of India for online Teaching-learning in a press conference discussed by the MHRD on March 21, 2020, the Union HRD Minister combined many free Online Learning platforms and digital modes for the students to resume their learning during Covid-19 based on school closings. The DIKSHA, e-Pathshala, The National Repository of Open Educational Resources (NROER) portal, Swayam Prabha, Swayam, CEC-UGC YouTube channel, National Digital Library, Shodhganga, e-Shodh Sindhu, etc. There are many live-video communication platforms are available on the internet such as Zoom, Google meets, Skype, Facebook Live, Youtube Live, Uber Conference, Free Conference, DingTalk, Lark, Teams, TrueConf Online, Slack Video Calls, Lifesize Go.

Interest and Motivation level of the students –“The impact of this lockdown is most exceedingly awful for the emotional wellness and satisfaction of a student, he/she can't meet his/her companions and appreciate what they used to do in pre-Coronavirus days. Beyond the electronic connection, we need to connect emotionally - - especially in times of anxiety and uncertainty. As a neuroscientist, I know that emotions are key to learning.”² Yet, presently, in lockdown, there is no inspiration for students to try and open their books. Since examines are totally on the web, from going to classes to transferring tasks for composing tests, numerous students have said they are thinking that it's hard to focus for long hours at a stretch. The students are feeling the loss of the

² Descartes' Error (Book)

Emotion, reason, and the human brain

By Antonio Damasio

Category: Psychology

daily schedule of a school and regardless of how much schools attempt to imitate it by requesting that they go to online classes in their uniform, it isn't the equivalent. Numerous guardians have said that youngsters continue "to snack" all through classes as certain instructors request that they keep the video and sound turned off or possibly they are compelled to keep them shut due to bad Net availability. At home, many can't keep themselves motivated and enthusiastic during online lectures.

Technical and Environmental Constraints during online teaching:- This advanced change of instructional conveyance accompanied a few strategic difficulties and attitudinal adjustments. (i) pandemic-related uneasiness will affect understudy scholastic execution, (ii) scholarly execution of the students may be influence by racial, financial and asset contrasts, and (iii) the wider group of educators were not viably prepared to convey top-notch teaching program distantly. The difficulties talked about here are restricted to advanced change of instructional tasks during the time of the Coronavirus pandemic.

Objectives of the study: Following are the different research objectives of the study.

1. To look at different online tools/platforms embraced by Educational\ organization amid the widespread Covid-19.
2. To recognize students' technological awareness regarding online Teaching-learning.
3. To highlight a few merits of the Online Teaching-Learning process.
4. To highlight a few demerits of the Online Teaching-Learning process.
5. To solicit the views of learners on online teaching learning-learning system all through the lockdown.

Research Methodology: The researcher takes an online survey on the efficacy of the online teaching-learning process during COVID 19 Pandemic. The researcher chooses 64 B.Ed students from three B.Ed Colleges namely Humera Khan College of Education, Andheri (west) Mumbai, Oriental College of Education and Research, Andheri (west) Mumbai and Dnyan Ganga College of Education, Thane (w) Maharashtra as the respondents through the non-probability convenience sampling techniques. The researcher does the item-wise analysis to find the answer to the following research questions. The study is limited to three B.Ed colleges' F.Y. and S.Y. students affiliated to Mumbai University only.

Research questions: Following are the different research questions of the study

Analysis of the Study: A survey on the efficacy of the online Teaching learning process during Covid 19. The following Pie chart and bar diagram shows the itemize analysis of the survey.

1. What are the different online tools/platforms embraced by Educational\ organization amid the widespread Covid-19?
2. What is the students' technological awareness regarding online Teaching-learning?
3. What are the merits of the Online Teaching-Learning process?
4. What are the demerits of the Online Teaching-Learning process?
5. What are the views of learners on online Teaching learning-learning system all through the lockdown?

Analysis of the Study: An online survey on the efficacy of the online Teaching-learning process during Covid 19. The following Pie charts show the itemize analysis of the survey.

The above bar chart is depicting that 22 or 34.378% students are learning on Google meet, 06 or 9.375% students are using google classroom, 01 or 1.56% student is using Blackboard, 01 or 1.56% student is using HTC, 01 or 1.56% student is using Microsoft, 19 students or 29.69% are using Zoom and 11 students are

saying they are not using any online platform for their studies. 4 students or 6.25% of students are using either zoom or Google for their online learning. The researcher uses the following questions to understand the students’ perspective of Online teaching-learning during the covid 19 pandemics. (Based on **5 point rating scale**- Strongly agree, agree, neither agree/nor disagree, disagree and strongly disagree)

Q.NO.	Questions with Bar diagram and the responses.												
1.	<p>You have adequate appliances and facilities (Sophisticated mobile/computer/laptop/Internet/software) for attending online lectures.</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Data for Q1: Adequate appliances and facilities</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5-strongly Agree</td> <td>18</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>38</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3-Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5-strongly Agree	18	4-Agree	38	3-Neither agree nor disagree	5	2-Disagree	2	1-Strongly Disagree	1
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2.	<p>You have enough computer knowledge and ICT expertise to cope with your online learning.</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Data for Q2: Computer knowledge and ICT expertise</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5-strongly Agree</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>35</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3-Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5-strongly Agree	10	4-Agree	35	3-Neither agree nor disagree	10	2-Disagree	5	1-Strongly Disagree	2
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3.	<p>Instructions are given (ex. how to handle proper online tools) before starting online classes by your institution.</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Data for Q3: Instructions given before starting classes</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5-strongly Agree</td> <td>19</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>33</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3-Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5-strongly Agree	19	4-Agree	33	3-Neither agree nor disagree	9	2-Disagree	3		
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4.	<p>Online tools are user friendly and easy to use.</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Data for Q4: Online tools user friendly and easy to use</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5-strongly Agree</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>39</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3-Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>11</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>4</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5-strongly Agree	10	4-Agree	39	3-Neither agree nor disagree	11	2-Disagree	4		
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<p>5.</p>	<p>You are satisfied with the online teaching methodology.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>33</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>13</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5- strongly Agree	7	4-Agree	33	3- Neither agree nor disagree	13	2-Disagree	8	1-Strongly Disagree	2
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<p>6.</p>	<p>Lack of interest in learning while being locked down has taken place.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>12</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>25</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>12</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>14</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5- strongly Agree	12	4-Agree	25	3- Neither agree nor disagree	12	2-Disagree	14	1-Strongly Disagree	1
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<p>7.</p>	<p>Online lectures are more effective than traditional classroom lectures.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>11</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>20</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>24</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>9</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5- strongly Agree	1	4-Agree	11	3- Neither agree nor disagree	20	2-Disagree	24	1-Strongly Disagree	9
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<p>8.</p>	<p>Using online learning is a kind of enjoyment.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>20</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>24</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>17</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5- strongly Agree	1	4-Agree	20	3- Neither agree nor disagree	24	2-Disagree	17	1-Strongly Disagree	3
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<p>9.</p>	<p>Gathered experience of learning in a new online platform.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>40</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>4</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5- strongly Agree	10	4-Agree	40	3- Neither agree nor disagree	7	2-Disagree	4		
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<p>10.</p>	<p>There is Flexibility in participating in online lectures.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>33</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>12</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5- strongly Agree	7	4-Agree	33	3- Neither agree nor disagree	12	2-Disagree	10	1-Strongly Disagree	0
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<p>11.</p>	<p>Lack of direct contact with other students/colleagues/friends is the cause of frustration.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>32</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>17</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5- strongly Agree	5	4-Agree	32	3- Neither agree nor disagree	10	2-Disagree	17	1-Strongly Disagree	0
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<p>12.</p>	<p>Inconsistent/poor contact and communication with the lecturers due to the technical glitches.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>30</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>18</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5- strongly Agree	10	4-Agree	30	3- Neither agree nor disagree	5	2-Disagree	18	1-Strongly Disagree	0
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<p>13.</p>	<p>Learning contents are difficult in online teaching than in that of the classroom.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>12</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>28</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>13</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5- strongly Agree	12	4-Agree	28	3- Neither agree nor disagree	10	2-Disagree	13	1-Strongly Disagree	0
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<p>14.</p>	<p>You are always highly motivated in participating online lectures.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>30</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>16</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>11</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	5- strongly Agree	5	4-Agree	30	3- Neither agree nor disagree	16	2-Disagree	11	1-Strongly Disagree	1
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<p>15.</p>	<p>You are happy about the student-teacher interaction during online teaching & learning process.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response Level</th> <th>Frequency</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>35</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response Level	Frequency	5- strongly Agree	10	4-Agree	35	3- Neither agree nor disagree	10	2-Disagree	5	1-Strongly Disagree	1
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<p>16.</p>	<p>You have the facility to ask your doubts during online lectures.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response Level</th> <th>Frequency</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>12</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>38</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>11</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response Level	Frequency	5- strongly Agree	12	4-Agree	38	3- Neither agree nor disagree	11	2-Disagree	2	1-Strongly Disagree	2
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<p>17.</p>	<p>Teachers' attention is less during an online session.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response Level</th> <th>Frequency</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>21</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>15</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>20</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>4</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response Level	Frequency	5- strongly Agree	4	4-Agree	21	3- Neither agree nor disagree	15	2-Disagree	20	1-Strongly Disagree	4
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<p>19.</p>	<p>Possibility of distractions from other family members during online lectures.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response Level</th> <th>Frequency</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5- strongly Agree</td> <td>14</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4-Agree</td> <td>31</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Neither agree nor disagree</td> <td>12</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2-Disagree</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-Strongly Disagree</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response Level	Frequency	5- strongly Agree	14	4-Agree	31	3- Neither agree nor disagree	12	2-Disagree	5	1-Strongly Disagree	1
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Final Thoughts- Through the above diagrams, and based on this study the researcher can conclude that most of the students are using Zoom, Google meet and Goole Classroom for their online studies. Online education has its good points and few drawbacks but seeing the current pandemic situation online platform has truly provided numerous opportunities for all of us to learn and make use of technology in making our lives easy and normal as per own comfort and convenience. According to the present scenario things are adapted to situations, still sitting and studying in a classroom and doing discussions with teachers and peers is another level of experience in the teaching-learning process. Online learning is new and a good platform of teaching-learning for all of us but due to lack of internet facility, disturbing home environment sometimes it's getting difficult to attend and remain in the lectures. Online Teaching provides knowledge about the future as it is an era of technology. It is okay to use these online platforms because of a pandemic but continue to use these platforms after a pandemic is not good at all for studies because it is difficult to understand some concepts in online mode. According to some responses, It's better to know about technology as respondents are the future teachers. They should know all the pros and cons of teaching as a teacher as well as students. Although face to face teaching is better than online teaching there are many things future teachers should know regarding the technology. Even technology should be used in traditional teaching to be more effective in the teaching and learning process.

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